

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2

ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

JENNIA NIKKA S. VILLON

Administrative Assistant III

Apayao State College

jenniansv@gmail.com

“SHADOWS IN THE LIGHT: THE HOME THAT NEVER WAS”

The walls are all sturdy, the roof keeps out rain,
The prettiest home for a heart to remain.
No fancy plates, no silk on the bed,
Just a quiet place for a tired head.
It was not built of bricks or stone,
But a kindness she'd never actually known.
A tiny kitchen, a narrow hall, with room for love to hold them all.

But that was a dream she had to keep,
A prayer she whispered before she'd sleep.
A whispered hope, a silent plea—
A home for the girl she will never be.
She would question herself, “Isn't this home supposed to be our safety net?”
Or perhaps it wasn't a net at all, but something that would let her fall.

Inside a quiet house that felt like glass,
She watched her childhood slowly pass.
She claims this home is her greatest pride,
But it is just a place she uses to hide
The floor felt heavy with fear, the light was blurred with every tear.
All she wanted is to fall asleep, to dream of life she was meant to keep.

The calm she kept was just a lie,
To hide how much she had to cry.
She made a world of 'if' and 'maybe',
to keep her inner child from being lonely.
The life she dreamed of was hers to keep,
She held a light while the world's asleep.
A flickering light to stay alive,
For a girl who was just trying to survive.

